

Inner Metallic Complexes of α -Benzoyl- β -Phenyl Thiocarbamide with Bivalent Metal Ions

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A few inner metallic complexes of the type, ML_xH_2O (where $M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Pd(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Pb(II)$ and $L = \alpha$ -Benzoyl- β -Phenyl thiocarbamide) are prepared and characterised. All the complexes are highly insoluble in water and also in common organic solvents. The ligand is coordinated to the metal ions through sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen atoms, as suggested from i.r. spectra. Basing on the electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements, an octahedral arrangement of the ligand around the metal ions has been proposed.

METAL complexes of ligands containing sulphur as donor atom are well documented¹⁻⁷. A recent review deals with the metal complexes of ligands containing sulphur-nitrogen and sulphur-nitrogen-oxygen as donor atoms⁸. It is well-known that metal complexes of sulphur donor ligands are of special importance due to wide range of their applicability and activity against viruses, protozoa, smallpox, cancer, tuberculosis and certain kinds of tumour⁹⁻¹². In view of the importance of metal complexes of sulphur donor ligands, we have reported the preparation of a few metal chelates of dithiocarbamides^{1,3}. In the present communication we describe the preparation and characterization of metal chelates of another sulphur-nitrogen-oxygen donor ligand, i.e., α -Benzoyl- β -Phenyl thiocarbamide.

Methods and Materials :

The ligand [$C_6H_5CONHCSNHC_6H_5$, abbreviated as ($H_2BzPhTC$)] was prepared following the

procedure reported by Horning¹⁴. (M. P. 154°; yield 80%).

Preparation of the Complexes :

An aqueous sodium salt solution of the ligand was added to an aqueous solution of the appropriate metal salts in the molar ratio 1 : 1. Complexes were immediately formed which was digested on a water bath for one hour. It was filtered, washed several times with water and finally with alcohol, dried in vacuum and analysed.

The metal content of each complex was determined according to standard procedures. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate¹⁵. The nitrogen content was determined by semi-micro combustion process. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE METAL CHELATES

Formula of the compounds	Colour	M. P. or Decomposition Temp. °C	# <i>eff</i> in B.M. at 32° ± 1°C	Metal%		Sulphur%		Nitrogen%	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. $[Cu(BzPhTC)]H_2O$	Light green	250 Decomposes	2.01	18.80	18.88	9.84	9.51	8.20	8.35
2. $[Ni(BzPhTC)]H_2O$	Greenish yellow	250	3.34	17.85	17.75	9.24	9.67	8.19	8.46
3. $[Co(BzPhTC)]H_2O$	Water-green	260	4.82	17.56	17.81	9.51	9.97	8.19	8.47
4. $[Mn(BzPhTC)]H_2O$	Roof-red	250	5.88	16.34	16.81	9.23	9.75	8.32	8.56
5. $[Pd(BzPhTC)]H_2O$	Chocolate	250	Diamagnetic	27.91	28.12	8.49	8.45	7.43	7.76
6. $[Zn(BzPhTC)]H_2O$	White	247 Decomposes	—	18.93	19.38	9.88	9.48	7.98	8.21
7. $[Cd(BzPhTC)]$	Yellowish white	250	—	27.97	27.86	7.81	7.96	7.58	7.64
8. $[Hg(BzPhTC)]$	White	250	—	39.86	40.88	6.83	6.52	5.78	6.15
9. $[Pb(BzPhTC)]1.5H_2O$	Grey	260	—	42.91	43.12	6.23	6.56	5.43	5.82

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The complexes were found to be insoluble in water and most of the common organic solvents.

Physical Measurements :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of these solid complexes at room temperatures were made by Gouy method, using mercury(II)-tetrathio-cyanato cobaltate(II) as the calibrating agent. The diamagnetic corrections were made using the values given by Lewis and Wilkins¹⁶. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes were recorded in KBr phase on Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes were taken by dissolving the freshly prepared samples in dioxan. The spectrum of the ligand was also taken in the UV region in methanol.

Results and Discussion

Infrared Spectra :

The ligand α -benzoyl- β -phenyl thiocarbamide may be postulated to exist in the following five different structural forms

The i.r. spectrum of the ligand shows strong and broad band in the region 3350-3050 cm^{-1} may be due to NH stretching frequency. The electronic spectrum of the ligand shows an intense band at ~ 250 nm and a weak band at 210 nm. These features in UV region are characteristics of a conjugated compound and provide evidence in favour of the structural form IV or its cis form V as the

predominant species. This led to believe that the ligand exists in equilibrium with keto(I) and enol(V) tautomeric forms.

Additional evidence against I, II, III and in favour of IV and V is obtained due to the existence of a weak band near 2460 cm^{-1} which originates due to (S-H) stretching vibration. This band disappears in all the metal complexes which are obtained as inner complex salts. The i.r. spectra of thiocarbamides and some of their metal complexes are known and show similar features in this region of the spectrum¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Most of the metal complexes isolated contain water of hydration which is reflected in their i.r. spectra by the appearance of a strong and broad band in the region 3600-3300 cm^{-1} . The width is due to hydrogen bonding. Besides, there appears a strong band at ~ 3000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to (CH) stretching vibration of phenyl groups.

The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in secondary amides is reported ~ 1680 cm^{-1} ^{20,21}. This band undergoes a shift in the metal complexes, suggesting coordination of C=O group to the metal ion through oxygen²². The band observed in the present study at 1690 cm^{-1} in the ligand may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration which suffers a shift to lower frequency region in all the metal complexes.

The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ band is reported in the region 1650 cm^{-1} , 1490 cm^{-1} and 1225 cm^{-1} in the free thiocarbamide but undergoes an increase on coordination to metal ions. In the present study the bands appearing at 1620 cm^{-1} and 1450 cm^{-1} in the free ligand may be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ which are found to shift to a higher frequency region or remain nearly unaffected.

The characteristic absorption region of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ is ~ 805 cm^{-1} as reported in the free thiocarbamide^{23,24}. Coordination of thiocarbamide to metal ion will decrease in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibration. The band appearing in the ligand spectrum ~ 790 cm^{-1} may be due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibration which is lowered to ~ 750 cm^{-1} on coordination to metal ions through sulphur atom.

Considering that the trans-structure of the ligand would be more stable than the cis-form and on the basis of above i.r. data we are led to suggest the following structure for the complexes.

Electronic Spectra and Magnetic Properties :

The copper complex possesses magnetic moment 2.01 B.M. and its electronic spectrum shows a broad asymmetric band whose maximum lies at 18,500 cm^{-1} followed by another medium band near 23,000 cm^{-1} . The former approximates to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$

transition in an approximately octahedral ligand field. The width and the asymmetry of this band suggests tetragonal distortion due to coordination to hetero atoms and also Jahn-Teller effect. The latter band arises due to charge transfer.

The nickel complex in the present investigation possesses magnetic moment 3.34 B.M. The electronic spectra of the nickel complex shows broad asymmetric band near $16,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by a strong intraligand transition band, the maxima of which lies near $24,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ligand field band can be assigned to the split components of ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ in octahedral approximation, i.e., ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ transitions in tetragonal ligand field mutually overlapping each other.

In the present study the magnetic moment of cobalt complex is 4.82 B.M. Its electronic spectrum shows an intense band at $15,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder at $17,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In an octahedral approximation these bands can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively.

The magnetic moment for the manganese(II) complex is found to be 5.88 B.M. which is the normal expected value of 5.9 B.M. for a spin free manganese(II) ion.

The palladium(II) Complex is diamagnetic.

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